

Our Heritage, Our Stories

Community Archives Digital Preservation Toolkit

This post-custodial toolkit is a key output developed by the Digital Preservation Coalition and the OHOS Archives Lab that provides community organisations with the means to effectively manage their own materials, adhering to a post-custodial approach that emphasises the importance of communities maintaining curatorial control over their own resources.

<https://www.dpconline.org/digipres/implement-digipres/community-archives-dp-toolkit>

<https://www.dpconline.org/blog/wdpd/opening-blog-william-kilbride-wdpd2024>